

STUDIES IN CARBOHYDRATES. PART VIII. STRUCTURE OF SWIETENOSE

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Swietenose, a new digalactoside, obtained from Gum Mokha, has been further purified to a white hygroscopic powder. The crude digalactoside has been methylated. The methylated product on vacuum distillation furnishes octa-*O*-methylidigalactoside (m.p. 130-31°; $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 130.9^\circ$) which on hydrolysis affords an equimolecular mixture of 2:3:4:6-tetra- and 2:3:4-tri-*O*-methyl-D-galactoses. The structure of the digalactoside has been suggested from periodate oxidation as 6-*O*- α -galactopyranosido-D-galactoside.

Isolation of swietenose, a new digalactoside, from Gum Mokha (*Schrebera swietenoides*, N.O. Oleaceae) with 90% ethanol was reported previously (this *Journal*, 1954, 33, 943). It was further purified by fractionating it on charcoal-xylosuperpel column (Whistler and Durso, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 677) using ethanol (5%) as an eluting solvent. The purified digalactoside fraction was concentrated to a syrup, which on trituration with absolute ethanol formed a white hygroscopic powder, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 142.5^\circ$ (*c*, 0.5% in water); its osazone had m.p. 193-94°.

The crude digalactoside was methylated by alkali and dimethyl sulphate and finally by Purdie's reagent. The methylated product, on distillation under reduced pressure, gave octa-*O*-methylidigalactoside, m.p. 130-31°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 130.9^\circ$ (*c*, 2% in methanol). On hydrolysis of the methylated derivative, an equimolecular mixture of 2:3:4:6-tetra-*O*-methyl-D-galactose and 2:3:4-tri-*O*-methyl-D-galactose was obtained. The identity of these sugars was confirmed (1) by their physical properties and R_f values, (2) by running chromatograms with authentic specimens of these sugars, and (3) by preparing their anilides, characterising them by their physical constants and finding mixed m.p. with the authentic samples of anilides.

The high positive rotations of the digalactoside and its methylated derivative indicate the presence of α -linkage. The digalactoside, swietenose, should therefore possess the following structure.

6-*O*- α -D-Galactopyranosido-D-galactose.

The above structure has also been supported by its periodate oxidation. During oxidation, five molecules of formic acid were liberated and six molecules of periodate

were consumed for one molecule of digalactoside. It appears that the same digalactoside has been isolated by Turton *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 2565) by the acid inversion of D-galactose.

EXPERIMENTAL

Isolation of Digalactoside.—Gum Mokha (25 g.) was extracted several times with 90% boiling ethanol till the residue did not show appreciable presence of mannitol chromatographically. It was dissolved in water, treated with charcoal and concentrated to a syrup. The concentrate was added to absolute alcohol (10 volumes), when the digalactoside precipitated as a white powder, yield 4 g. This was recognised as a crude digalactoside.

The crude digalactoside (2 g.) was completely separated from mannitol by fractionating it on charcoal-hyflsuperpel column with elution by ethanol (5%). The pure digalactoside fraction was concentrated to a syrup under reduced pressure and added to absolute alcohol, when it was obtained as a white powder, yield 1.5 g. It did not crystallise, but it was found to be hygroscopic; $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 142.5^\circ$ (*c*, 0.5% in water). It gave an osazone, m.p. 193-94°.

Methylation of the Digalactoside.—The crude digalactoside (10 g.) was methylated by dimethyl sulphate (150 c.c.) and sodium hydroxide (150 c.c., 50%) at room temperature four times. The reaction mixture was heated to 80° for 1 hour and extracted with chloroform (5 × 100 c.c.). The chloroform extract was washed with saturated sodium sulphate solution, dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate and the solvent was removed, yield 10 g. (Found: OMe, 50.5%); $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 125^\circ$ (*c*, 2% in chloroform). The residue was methylated twice, by using methyl iodide (100 c.c.) and silver oxide (30 g.) each time, when a semi-solid was obtained. (Found: OMe, 55.5%); $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 129.2^\circ$ (*c*, 2% in chloroform). Further methylation did not raise the methoxyl content. When the product was subjected to vacuum distillation, octa-*O*-methyl digalactoside distilled at 280-90°/1.3 mm as a viscous syrup, which slowly solidified. It is soluble in ether, acetone, ethyl and methyl alcohols, benzene and sparingly soluble in petroleum ether; yield 5 g. It crystallised in fine needles from ether-petroleum ether mixture, m.p. 130-31°; $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 130.9^\circ$ (*c*, 2% in methanol). (Found: C, 52.9; H, 8.7; OMe, 54.5. $C_{20}H_{32}O_{11}$ requires C, 52.83; H, 8.43; OMe, 54.63%).

*Hydrolysis of Octa-*O*-methyl digalactoside.*—The methylated sugar (0.8 g.) was hydrolysed by 1*N*-HCl at 90° for 12 hrs. Neutralisation with silver carbonate, followed by hydrogen sulphide treatment to remove Ag⁺ ions, gave a filtrate, which on concentration furnished a mixture of methylated sugars as a syrup (0.75 g., 90%). Chromatographic examination showed the presence of two sugars, which were found to be 2:3:4:6-tetra-*O*-methyl-D-galactose and 2:3:4 tri-*O*-methyl-D-galactose by running authentic samples side by side. These sugars were separated on a cellulose column (70 × 6 cm) by eluting them with benzene-ethanol-water (169:47:15) mixture.

(1) 2:3:4:6-Tetra-*O*-methyl-D-galactose (0.33 g.) had OMe, 52.1%, $[\alpha]_D^{27} + 60.2$ (*c*, 2% in ethanol). Calc. for $C_{18}H_{26}O_8$: OMe, 52.5%; $[\alpha]_D + 62.6^\circ$ (Irvine and Cameron, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 85, 1071). It gave an anilide which crystallised in wooly needles from alcohol, m.p. 193-94° (mixed m.p. 194°).

(2) 2:3:4-Tri-*O*-methyl-D-galactose (0.3 g.) had OMe, 41.3%; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$, + 142° (c, 2% in water) which finally changed to +114°. Calc. for $C_8H_{18}O_6$: OMe, 41.9%; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$, +142° $\rightarrow$ +114° (McCreath and Smith, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 389). It gave an anilide, m.p. 164-65°; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$, + 40° (c, 1% in MeOH); (OMe, 31.6; N, 4.9%); (mixed m.p. 165°).

TABLE I

Periodate oxidation of the digalactoside.

Time (hours)	...	...	0.5	1	2	4	6
Mols. of HIO_4 consumed for one mol. of							
Digalactoside	...	...	5.4	5.65	5.8	5.9	6.0
Melibiose	...	...	5.5	5.7	5.9	6.05	6.05
Lactose	...	...	4.05	4.7	5.05	5.1	5.1
Mols. of formic acid liberated for one mol. of							
Digalactoside	...	...	4.2	4.4	4.55	4.9	5.0
Melibiose	...	...	4.3	4.5	4.7	5.0	5.05
Lactose	...	...	2.7	2.8	3.0	3.1	3.15

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